

WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH SELF HELP GROUPS IN TAMIL NADU, INDIA

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Abstract

Self-help groups are started by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) that generally have broad anti-poverty agendas. Self-help groups are seen as instruments for goals including empowering women, developing leadership abilities among poor people, increasing school enrollments, and improving nutrition and the use of birth control. Financial intermediation is generally seen more as an entry point to these other goals, rather than as a primary objective. This can hinder their development as sources of village capital, as well as their efforts to aggregate locally controlled pools of capital through federation, as was historically accomplished by credit unions. Keeping this in mind the researcher made study. A study on original and women empowerment through self help groups in India. Research data have been collected from various available sources.

Key words: *Self Help Groups, Goal, NGO, NABARD*

Origin of Self Help Groups

Self-help groups (SHGs) first emerged in MYRADA in 1985. In 1986/87 there were some 300 SHGs in MYRADA's projects. Many had emerged from the breakdown of the large cooperatives organized by MYRADA.² In these areas, a number of members asked MYRADA to revive the credit system. They usually came in groups of 15-20. When reminded of the loans they had taken out from the cooperative, they offered to return them to MYRADA, but not to the cooperative, which in their experience was dominated by a few individuals. MYRADA staff suggested that they return the money to themselves - in other words to the members who had come in a group to present their case to MYRADA. After some hesitation, they decided to continue meeting in these smaller groups. MYRADA staff realized that they would need training: how to organize a meeting, set an agenda, keep minutes, etc. Efforts were made to train the members systematically. On analysis it emerged that the members were linked together by a degree of affinity based on relationships of trust and support; they were also often homogeneous in terms of income or of occupation (for example, agricultural laborers), but not always. Caste and creed played a role, but in several groups affinity relationships and economic homogeneity were stronger; as a result, several groups included different castes and creeds. From the time that the first SHGs emerged in 1985 to the inclusion of the SHG strategy in the annual plan for 2000/01 (Government of India, 2000), several important steps were taken by the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD), the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) and leading NGOs, as well as by multilateral agencies, particularly IFAD.³ The SHG strategy is an important component of the Government's overall thrust to mitigate poverty and has been included in every annual plan since 2000. This period of 20 years can be divided broadly into two phases.

Self Help Groups From 1987-1992

During this phase - largely omitted in recent studies - NABARD focused on supporting NGO initiatives to promote SHGs and on analyzing their potential and performance. In 1987 NABARD first put funds into the SHG/SAG⁴ movement (in response to a proposal from MYRADA submitted in 1986). In 1987 it provided MYRADA with a grant of 1 million Indian rupees (Rs) 5 to enable it to invest resources to identify affinity groups, build their capacity and match their savings after a period of 3-6 months. The grant was based on MYRADA's experience in promoting SHGs since 1985 and the initiative of the NABARD chairperson at that time, Shri P.R. Nayak. As a result of the feedback from this initiative, in 1989 NABARD launched an action research project in which similar grants were provided to other NGOs. After an analysis of this action research, and owing to the efforts of successive NABARD chairpersons and senior management, in 1990 RBI accepted the SHG strategy as an alternative credit model. NABARD (1992) issued guidelines to provide the framework for a strategy that would allow banks to lend directly to SHGs. Based on these initial experiences,

the SHG-Bank Linkage Programme was launched in 1992 (this second phase is described in Section III). Since then - and on the basis of its extensive network of officers - NABARD has promoted and monitored the SHG programme, provided funds for capacity building and innovation, and helped change policy to create an enabling environment. The Tamil Nadu Women's Empowerment Project, an IFAD-supported project implemented through the Tamil Nadu Women's Development Corporation, was the first project in the country, in about 1990, to incorporate the SHG concept into a state sponsored programmed. MYRADA was asked to play a lead role, which it agreed to do in Dharmapuri District. This was a year or more before the launch of the SHG-Bank Linkage Programmed. The empowerment of women was sought through SHG strengthening, with capacity-building modules, and through the provision of credit for income-generating activities.

Evolution of the SHG Movement in India

The first organized initiative in this direction was taken in Gujarat in 1954 when the Textile Labor Association (TLA) of Ahmadabad formed its women's wing to organize the women belonging to households of mill workers in order to train them in primary skills like sewing, knitting embroidery, typesetting and stenography etc. In 1972, it was given a more systematized structure when Self Employed Women's Association (SEWA) was formed as a Trade Union under the leadership of Ela Bhatt. She organized women workers such as hawkers, vendors, home based operators like weavers, potters, papad / agarbatti makers, manual laborers', service providers and small producers like cattle rearers, salt workers, gum collectors, cooks and vendors with the primary objective of (a) increasing their income and assets; (b) enhancing their food and nutritional standards; and (c) increasing their organizational and leadership strength. The overall intention was to organize women for full employment. In order to broaden their access to market and technical inputs, these primary associations were encouraged to form federations like the Gujarat State Mahila SEWA Cooperative Federation, Banaskantha DWCRA, and Mahila SEWA Association etc. Currently, SEWA has a membership strength of 9, 59,000 which is predominantly urban. In the 1980s, Myrada - a Karnataka based non-governmental organization, promoted several locally formed groups to enable the members to secure credit collectively and use it along with their own savings for activities which could provide them economically gainful employment. Major experiments in small group formation at the local level were initiated in Tamilnadu and Kerala about two decades ago through the Tamilnadu Women in Agriculture Programmed (TANWA) 1986, Participatory Poverty Reduction Programme of Kerala, (Kudumbashree) 1995 and Tamilnadu Women's Development Project (TNWDP) 1989. These initiatives gave a firm footing to SHG movement in this State. Today, around 44% of the total Bank-linked SHGs of the country are in the four southern States of Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka and Kerala.4.3.1.3 The positive experience gained from the above programmes has led to the emergence of a very strong consensus that the twin concepts of (a) small group organization and (b) self-management are potent tools for economic and social empowerment of the rural poor. Efforts have been made almost in all parts of the country to adopt this model as a necessary component of the poverty alleviation programmes.

Table 1 Grant Assistance Extended to SHIPs as on 31.03.2016

(Rs. In Lakh)

S. No	Agency	Cumulative Position up to 31.03.2016			
		No of SHG Sanctioned	Amount Sanctioned	No of SHG Promoted	Amount released
1.	NGOs	6,50,132	30,475	4,58,033	10,308
2.	NGO - MFIs	0	0	0	0
3.	RRBs	56,048	1,341	44,344	324
4.	CO-operative Banks	68,762	1,072	55,126	482
5.	IRVs	29,810	514	14,084	88
6.	Farmer's Clubs	5,098	41	1,995	21
7.	Self Federation	300	32	195	15
8.	PALS	13,430	593	1,601	57
	Total	8,23,580	34,068	5,75,378	11,295

Source: Annual Report, NABARD - 2015-2016

That the table 1 reveals the cumulative assistance sanctioned to various agencies was Rs.340.68 crore for promoting 8.23 lakh SHGs against which assistance of Rs.112.95 crore was released for formation of 5.75 lakh SHGs as on 31.03.2016.

Table 2 Progress of SHG - Bank Linkage Programs (as on 31.03.2016)

S. No	Particulars	2014		Amount in Rs. Cr 2015	
		Number of SHGs	Amount	Number SHGs	Amount
1.	Loan distributed	13,66,421	24,017	16,26,238	27,582
2.	Loan Outstanding	41,97,338	42,927	44,68,180	51,545
3.	Savings with banks	74,29,500	9,897	76,97,469	11,059
	Total	1,29,93,259	76,841	1,37,91,887	43,796

Source: Annual Report, NABARD - 2015-2016

Table 2 depicts the rural poor, thought to be unbendable prior to the SHG-Bank linkage programme now constitute a staggering 4.4 million SHGs having credit outstanding of Rs. 51,545 crore in the formal lending institution About 1.6 million SHGs had availed credit support of Rs. 27,582 from various bank

Table 3 Region wise status of Bank Loan Distributed to SHGs during 2015-2016
(Total Loan Distributed [Rs. in Lakh: Average was distributed in Rs/SHGs])

Regions	2013-2014			2014-2015			2015-2016		
	No of SHGs	Total Loans Distributed	Average Loan Distributed	No of SHGs	Total Loans Distributed	Average Loan Distributed	No of SHGs	Total Loans Distributed	Average Loan Distributed
North Eastern	16201	12819	79125	18791	15795	84056	26037	21969	84375
Northern	23918	28048	117269	43848	42873	97777	38106	48298	126746
Central	66393	61807	93092	109231	110909	101536	84282	119067	141272
Western	87846	86444	98404	97341	117080	120279	112525	188632	167636
Eastern	297478	151067	50783	351800	329602	93690	412576	349486	84709
Southern	874585	2061551	234718	1005227	2141972	213083	1158797	3001235	258996
All India	1366421	2401736	175768	1626238	2758231	169608	1832323	3728690	203495

Source: Annual Report - NABARD - 2015-2016

Table 3 describes the numbers of SHGs availing bank loan, total amount of credit disbursed by banks as well as the average credit disbursement to SHG's in different Regions during past three years are given in Table. There was 35% jump in quantum of credit disbursement in 2015-16 compared to 15% last year and 20% jump in average credit disbursement per SHG compared to a decline of 3.5%. The states of Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Karnataka, Tamilnadu and West Bengal were the major contributions to this quantum growth.

Self Help Groups In Tamilnadu

Self Help Group (SHG) is a group of 12 to 20 women of the same socio-economic background who come forward voluntarily to work together for their own upliftment. The unique feature of the SHG is its ability to inculcate among its members sound habits of thrift, savings and banking.

Regular savings, periodic meetings, compulsory attendance, and systematic training are the salient features of the SHG concept. Each group selects one animator and two representatives from among themselves. The animator is responsible for providing leadership to the group and to maintain the various registers. The representatives assist the animator and maintain the bank accounts of the group.

- Self Help Groups consist of 12-20 BPL women members in the age group 18-60 years residing in the same area.
- NGOs and PLFs affiliated with TNCDW undertake the formation of SHGs.

- They are trained to become cohesive as a group through regular meetings and encouraged to cultivate savings habit.
- Capacity Building Programmes such as SHG and A & R training are imparted to the Group members and within a period of six months.
- After a period of 6 months, SHGs are rated for Credit Linkage by a Committee consisting of Bankers, APOs, NGOs, Block level officer and PLF Representative.
- For the eligible Credit rated SHGS, credit facilities are largely made available through Banks, both for revolving fund and economic activity.
- Other sources of funding for Credit linkage are SGSY, TAHDCO, NABARD & SJSRY
- Under various Skill Training Programmes, eligible SHG members are encouraged to start economic activities or undertake self employment.
- Efforts are made by TNCDW for marketing the products produced by SHGs wherever possible locally and for sale in exhibitions.

In order to enable all poor women living below poverty line to join and benefit from the Self Help Group movement, the group formation is undertaken with special focus on NREGS women workers, urban slum dwellers and in Village Panchayats where SHG coverage is still inadequate. Hence, Tamil Nadu will have the distinction of enrolling all women living below the poverty line into SHG movement.

Table 4 Group Formation in Tamilnadu top Ten Districts
(Rural Women Self Help Groups formed by TNCDN as on 31.02.2012)

S. No	District	Rural No. of Groups	Rank	No. of Members	Rank
1	Villupuram	21,886	I	3,36,630	I
2	Kanchipuram	19,928	II	3,07,363	II
3	Thiruvannamalai	18,124	III	2,06,673	III
4	Vellore	17,168	IV	2,64,677	IV
5	Cuddalore	16,484	V	2,55,320	V
6	Thanjavur	15,841	VI	2,41,905	VI
7	Tirunelveli	14,519	VII	2,01,928	VII
8	Nagapattinam	13,604	VIII	2,10,289	VIII
9	Trichy	13,503	IX	2,07,546	IX
10	Thiruvallur	13,347	X	2,26,241	X
11	Other districts	2,07,688		24,58,572	
	Total	3,72,092		57,37,023	

Source: <http://www.tamilnadumahalir.org>

Table 4 shows that Vilupuram district is the first place for Group formation in Tamilnadu Rural Women Self Help Groups among all district and followed by Kanchipuram, Thiruvannamalai the place of second and third respectively group formation in Tamilnadu Rural Women self help group.

Table 5 Group Formation in Tamilnadu top Ten Districts
(Urban Women Self Help Groups formed by TNCDW as on 31.03.2012)

S. No	District	Rural No. of Groups	Rank	No. of Members	Rank
1	Chennai	31,344	I	4,83,322	I
2	Kanyakumari	9,583	II	1,47,590	II
3	Coimbatore	9,545	III	1,47,273	III
4	Salem	9,330	IV	1,43,079	IV
5	Kanchipuram	9,307	V	1,42,832	V
6	Tirunelveli	9,111	VI	88,025	X
7	Thiruvallur	8,127	VII	1,39,407	VI
8	Erode	7,468	VIII	1,15,432	VII
9	Trichy	6,785	IX	1,04,454	VIII

10	Madurai	6,407	X	98,522	IX
11	Other districts	77,212		12,22,718	
	Total	1,84,219		28,32,654	

Source: <http://www.tamilnadumahalir.org>

Table 5 exhibit that Group formation and number of members in TamilNadu Urban Women Self Help Groups Chennai District is the first rank and followed by Kanniyakumari and Coimbatore the place of second and third respectively Groups and number of members in urban women self help group.

Recommendations

- The role of the Government in the growth and development of the SHG movement should be that of a facilitator and promoter. The objective should be to create a supportive environment for this movement.
- Since a large number of rural households in the North-Eastern States and Central-Eastern parts of the country (Bihar, Jharkhand, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Orissa, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh and Rajasthan) do not have adequate access to formal sources of credit, a major thrust on the expansion of the SHG movement in these areas should be facilitated. The presence of NABARD should be much more pronounced in these places.
- The SHG movement needs to be extended to urban and peri-urban areas. State Governments, NABARD and commercial Banks should join together to prepare a directory of activities and financial products relevant to such areas.
- The SHG - Bank Linkage model with a mentor SHPI in tow deserves to be encouraged as the preferred mode for financial intermediation throughout the country.
- There should be a planned effort to establish RRB networks in the 87 districts of the country which currently do not have RRB presence.
- Special steps should be taken for training / capacity building of government functionaries so that they develop a positive attitude and treat the poor and marginalized as viable and responsible customers and as possible entrepreneurs.
- There is need to review the scale of the promotional grant given to SHPIs by NABARD (currently Rs.1500/- per SHG formed and activated).
- There must be lot more publicity given among the potential beneficiaries about the schemes and contents as well as the authorities in charge and their responsibility.

Conclusion

If self help groups members is given systematic guidance and innovative training method to enhance the area of the group service future will be bright prosperous. The governments have taken special efforts to increase the quantum of credit to self help groups and ensure credit is made available to SHGs in multiple does. Government provide interest free subsidized loan to self help groups to help them come out of poverty.

References

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